

Medical University
Prof. Dr. Paraskev Stoyanov
Varna, Bulgaria

Scripta Scientifica Pharmaceutica

volume 11, 2024, supplement 1

ISSN 2367-6000

SSP

Scripta Scientifica Pharmaceutica

volume 11, 2024, supplement 1

ISSN 2367-6000 (print)
ISSN 2367-5500 (online)

Scripta Scientifica Pharmaceutica

An official publication of Medical University "Prof. Dr. Paraskev Stoyanov" of Varna

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**Tenth Pharmaceutical Business Forum
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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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November 07–09, 2024**

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THE EXPANDING ROLE OF THE HOSPITAL PHARMACIST: ENACTING A MULTIDISCIPLINARY TEAM STRATEGIES FOR PATIENTS WITH HEMATOLOGICAL DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: The expanding role of hospital pharmacists in the multidisciplinary on-site care of patients with hematological diseases has gained increasing recognition. The integration of pharmacists into healthcare teams is particularly crucial for patients receiving complex therapies, such as oral cytostatics, where coordinated care is essential.

AIM: The aim is to assess the effectiveness of multidisciplinary strategies involving hospital pharmacists in the care of patients with hematological diseases, with a focus on identifying best practices and areas for possible improvement.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: A systematic literature review was conducted using the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines. Peer-reviewed articles published between 2010 and 2023 were sourced from databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science. Inclusion criteria were studies that examined hospital pharmacists' involvement in multidisciplinary teams and their impact on patient care, specifically in hematology. The selection process followed the PRISMA framework, including title/abstract screening and full-text review.

RESULTS: The PRISMA analysis revealed that the most effective strategies involving hospital pharmacists include medication therapy management, patient counseling, participation in clinical rounds, and collaboration with hematologists and nursing staff. Studies show that pharmacist-led interventions significantly improve patient adherence to oral cytostatic therapies, reduce medication errors, and enhance overall treatment outcomes. Furthermore, patient satisfaction and healthcare professional collaboration were notably improved when pharmacists were fully integrated into the care team.

CONCLUSION: Hospital pharmacists are crucial in multidisciplinary care for hematological patients, with evidence supporting their positive impact on clinical outcomes and patient safety. Further research is recommended to optimize and expand their role in patient care.

Keywords: *hospital pharmacist, multidisciplinary care, hematological diseases, oral cytostatics*